

THE IMPACT OF THE 2022 ENERGY CRISIS ON UK ELECTRICITY SYSTEM
PRICES: A COMMODITY MARKET ANALYSIS

PRIYANKA NAIK

FINAL THESIS REPORT

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DECLARATION

I, Priyanka Naik, declare that this dissertation titled “**Analyzing the Impact of the 2022 Energy Crisis on UK Electricity System Prices**” is entirely my own work, submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Business Administration at Liverpool John Moore's University under the guidance of **Dr. Vasileios Pappas**.

All sources of direct quotations and references have been duly acknowledged in the text and listed in full in the reference list. This dissertation has not been submitted, either in whole or in part, for any other degree or qualification at this or any other institution.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BMRS	Balancing Mechanism Reporting Service
BoE	Bank of England
BP	Brent Crude Oil Price
CPI	Consumer Price Index
EIA	U.S. Energy Information Administration
EPU	Economic Policy Uncertainty Index
EU	European Union
FTAS	FTSE All-Share Index
GARCH	Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GFC	Global Financial Crisis
GPR	Geopolitical Risk
GRI	Geopolitical Risk Index
HAR	Heterogeneous Autoregressive Model
IEA	International Energy Agency
IMF	International Monetary Fund
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
MPC	Monetary Policy Committee (Bank of England)
MW	Megawatt
MWh	Megawatt-hour
NGP	Natural Gas Price
OFGEM	Office of Gas and Electricity Markets
OPEC	Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries
OPU	Oil Price Uncertainty Index
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
RQ	Research Question
SAP	System Average Price (of Natural Gas)
SVAR	Structural Vector Autoregression
UK	United Kingdom
USD	United States Dollar
VAR	Vector Autoregression
WTI	West Texas Intermediate Crude Oil

ABSTRACT

The 2022 energy crisis, triggered by Russia-Ukraine war, geopolitical tensions and supply chain disruptions, significantly impacted global commodity markets, with far-reaching consequences for the energy sector. This study investigates the effect of the 2022 energy crisis on UK electricity system prices, employing a multiple regression analysis of daily electricity price data alongside key commodity prices such as oil and natural gas. The analysis reveals a significant correlation between fluctuations in energy commodity prices and electricity prices in the UK, highlighting the vulnerability of the electricity market to global energy supply disruptions. The study also compares the impact of this crisis with previous energy shocks, providing valuable insights into the persistence and intensity of price volatility. Our findings suggest that the 2022 energy crisis has led to heightened volatility in electricity prices, with implications for both consumers and policymakers. The paper concludes with policy recommendations for improving the resilience of the UK electricity system in the face of future energy crises.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 CONTEXT AND BACKGROUND

Commodity markets are highly sensitive to global economic fluctuations, shifts in supply-demand dynamics and geopolitical developments. Among these, energy commodities, such as crude oil and natural gas, are particularly volatile due to their central role in industrial activity, transportation and electricity generation. Over the past two decades, multiple crises have highlighted how disruptions in energy markets can have far-reaching economic consequences. Notable events including the 2008 Global Financial Crisis (GFC) and the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrated the profound impact such shocks can have on energy prices, with significant implications for the broader economy. The most recent of these crises, the 2022 energy crisis, which was triggered by the post-pandemic economic recovery and exacerbated by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, has further reshaped global energy price dynamics. This crisis has led to unprecedented levels of volatility in electricity markets, particularly in the UK.

Prior to 2021, global energy prices experienced relative stability, marked by occasional fluctuations driven by factors such as supply chain issues, trade disputes, and short-term economic downturns. However, from mid-2021 onward, global energy markets entered a phase of sharp upward price movements due to a combination of factors. These included the post-pandemic surge in energy demand as countries lifted COVID-19 restrictions, which outpaced supply. Additionally, a structural shift away from fossil fuel investments, along with pandemic-induced reductions in oil and gas production, created supply constraints that further exacerbated price increases. Geopolitical tensions, particularly between Russia and Western nations, intensified the crisis, raising concerns about energy security in Europe and driving risk premiums in commodity markets higher.

The crisis reached its peak in February 2022 when Russia, one of the largest global exporters of natural gas (accounting for 17% of global supply) and crude oil (accounting for 11% of global supply), launched a full-scale invasion of Ukraine. In response, the European Union, the United States, and the UK imposed sanctions on Russian oil and gas exports, which led to additional disruptions in supply chains. As a result, electricity prices across Europe, including the UK, soared to record levels. Figure 1 illustrates the significant increase in commodity prices from 2021 to 2023, highlighting the extreme volatility that these geopolitical events have caused in global energy markets.

Figure 1: Trends in Commodity Prices (2021-2023)

1.2 UK ELECTRICITY PRICING AND MARKET DYNAMICS

In the UK, electricity pricing is primarily determined by the marginal cost of electricity generation, meaning that the most expensive fuel source dictates the market price in wholesale electricity markets. Given that natural gas accounts for over 40% of the country's electricity generation, fluctuations in gas prices play a significant role in determining the overall electricity price. Unlike oil, which is primarily used in transportation and industrial sectors, natural gas serves as a direct input in electricity production. This distinction makes natural gas prices more influential in determining electricity prices than oil prices, even though both are essential energy commodities.

Prior research has shown strong co-movements between natural gas prices and electricity prices, particularly in markets where gas-fired power plants dominate the energy mix (Apergis & Payne, 2014; Mohammadi & Parvaresh, 2014). In such markets, natural gas price fluctuations directly affect the cost of electricity generation, and thus, the price paid by consumers. However, this relationship is not always straightforward. Macroeconomic factors such as government interventions, supply chain disruptions, and broader financial market conditions can distort the correlation between gas prices and electricity prices.

To further explore the relationship between UK electricity prices and key influencing factors, two correlation matrices were constructed using historical daily and monthly datasets. The first matrix, displayed in **Table 1**, quantifies the relationship between electricity prices, natural gas prices, Brent crude oil prices, and key macroeconomic indicators such as the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), UK Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) index and the FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS). This matrix, derived from daily log return data spanning January

2021 to December 2023, provides a detailed view of how electricity prices correlate with broader economic factors.

Daily Correlation Matrix	Variable	Electricity	Natural Gas	Brent Oil	UK EPU Daily	FTSE All-Share
	Electricity	1.00	0.35	-0.01	0.01	-0.03
	Natural Gas	0.35	1.00	0.11	0.06	-0.03
	Brent Spot	-0.01	0.11	1.00	0.00	0.21
	UK EPU Daily	0.01	0.06	0.00	1.00	-0.04
	FTSE All-Share	-0.03	-0.03	0.21	-0.04	1.00

Table 1: Daily Correlation Matrix (Electricity Prices vs. Other Economic Variables)

A second correlation matrix, presented in **Table 2**, examines the relationship between electricity prices and the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), which is available only at a monthly frequency. To maintain consistency in the analysis, electricity price data were aggregated to a monthly level before computing the correlations with the GPR. This matrix highlights the impact of geopolitical risk on electricity prices, offering insights into how geopolitical events influence energy pricing.

Monthly Correlation Matrix	Variable	Electricity
	GPR	0.15

Table 2: Monthly Correlation Matrix (Electricity Prices vs. Geopolitical Risk Index)

These matrices help identify the primary drivers of electricity price fluctuations and assess the extent to which economic and geopolitical factors influence market dynamics

To further illustrate this dynamic, **Figure 2** presents a scatter plot that visualizes the relationship between daily natural gas prices and electricity prices in the UK over the 2021-2023 period. The pattern observed suggests a moderate correlation (0.35), confirming the significant role of natural gas prices as a key player in influencing electricity costs.

Figure 2: Scatter Plot of Natural Gas Prices vs. UK Electricity Prices (2021-2023)

While natural gas prices have a clear impact on electricity pricing, the influence of Brent crude oil prices remains less certain. Previous studies (Hamilton, 2009; Kilian, 2014) suggest that oil price shocks tend to affect broader economic conditions rather than directly influencing electricity costs. As shown in Figure 3, the correlation between Brent crude oil prices and electricity prices is negligible (-0.01), suggesting that oil market volatility does not directly translate into electricity pricing fluctuations.

Figure 3: Scatter Plot of Brent Crude Oil Prices vs. UK Electricity Prices (2021-2023)

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Given the observed market trends and the limitations in existing research, this study aims to answer three key research questions:

- **RQ-1:** Are natural gas and Brent crude oil prices significantly correlated with UK electricity prices?
- **RQ-2:** How have post-COVID geopolitical events influenced this relationship?

- **RQ-3:** Do broader economic uncertainties, such as those captured by the GPR, EPU, and FTAS indices, have a more pronounced impact on electricity prices compared to the effect of Brent crude oil and natural gas prices?

This study seeks to provide empirical evidence on the drivers of electricity price volatility by integrating energy price movements with macroeconomic factors like geopolitical risk (GPR), economic policy uncertainty (EPU), and financial market performance (FTSE All Share Index - FTAS). The findings will offer data-driven insights to policymakers, helping them design strategies to mitigate future energy crises.

1.4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To analyze the relationship between commodity prices and electricity pricing, this study employs a combination of descriptive statistics, correlation coefficient analysis, scatter plot analysis and regression modelling. Descriptive statistics are used to examine historical trends in electricity, gas, and oil prices from 2021 to 2023, providing an initial understanding of the data. Correlation analysis is then applied to quantify the relationships between electricity prices and key economic variables.

A multiple regression model is used to evaluate the impact of natural gas and oil prices, alongside macroeconomic indicators, on UK electricity prices. By comparing pre-crisis (2021) and post-crisis (2023) models, the study seeks to identify structural changes in the relationship between commodity prices and electricity pricing due to the energy crisis. Additionally, event-based analysis is employed to assess whether major geopolitical events in the year 2022 (such as the Russia-Ukraine war, UK energy price cap changes, interest rate hikes, etc.) have caused significant shifts in energy price relationships. By employing this comprehensive analytical approach, this study aims to differentiate between direct energy market effects and broader macroeconomic influences, ultimately enhancing our understanding of electricity price drivers in times of crisis.

1.5 KEY CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STUDY

While existing research has examined the role of commodity prices in electricity markets, this study makes several distinct contributions. First, it integrates key macroeconomic indicators, such as the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU), and FTSE All Share Index (FTAS), offering a broader economic context to the analysis of energy price volatility. Second, by analysing structural changes in energy price relationships and comparing pre- and post-crisis periods, the study identifies whether the 2022 energy crisis has permanently altered market dynamics. Finally, the empirical findings from this study provide valuable insights for policymakers, helping to design interventions that stabilize energy markets and enhance resilience in the face of future crises.

1.6 REPORT STRUCTURE

The remainder of this dissertation is structured as follows. Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive review of the literature and prior studies on energy price volatility, electricity markets, and economic uncertainty. Chapter 3 outlines the research design, data sources, and regression framework used in the study. Chapter 4 presents the empirical findings, including the results from the regression models and exploratory data analysis. Chapter 5 discusses the findings in relation to the research questions, interpretations of the results and policy implications. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the study by summarizing the contributions, limitations, and directions for future research. By addressing these themes, this study contributes to both academic research and practical energy policy, offering actionable insights for navigating electricity market volatility in the post-crisis era.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO COMMODITY PRICE DYNAMICS AND ENERGY MARKETS

Commodity markets are often marked by complex interconnections and fluctuations, with price movements influenced by a variety of factors, including supply-demand imbalances, geopolitical events, macroeconomic policies, and speculative trading. In particular, energy commodities, such as crude oil and natural gas, are characterized by considerable volatility due to their fundamental role in industrial activity, transportation, and electricity generation. The literature on commodity price dynamics is vast, with seminal studies highlighting the crucial impact of energy price fluctuations on the broader economy. One of the key contributors to this literature, [Hamilton \(2009\)](#), emphasizes the critical role of oil price shocks in driving global economic fluctuations. Oil markets, with their relatively inelastic demand and strong geopolitical dependencies, have been shown to transmit volatility across different sectors, as noted by [Baffes \(2007\)](#) and [Kilian \(2014\)](#).

The relationship between energy commodity prices and the broader economy is often shaped by investor sentiment and macroeconomic uncertainty. [Pindyck & Rotemberg \(1990\)](#) argue that excessive co-movement among commodity prices can occur when factors like investor perceptions and broader economic shocks override traditional supply-demand interactions. [Caldara, Cavallo & Iacoviello \(2019\)](#) extend this argument by demonstrating that external shocks, such as financial crises or military conflicts, significantly amplify energy price volatility. However, despite extensive research on energy commodity prices, the impact of these price fluctuations on electricity markets remains less explored.

[Zhang et al. \(2021\)](#) note that although crude oil prices have historically had a significant influence on energy markets, natural gas has emerged as a dominant driver of electricity prices in recent years, particularly in deregulated markets. This shift is particularly relevant to the UK electricity market, where gas-fired power generation accounts for a large portion of the energy mix ([Apergis & Payne, 2014](#)).

Commodity price fluctuations are a fundamental aspect of global economic systems, influenced by a wide range of macroeconomic, geopolitical, and financial factors ([Hamilton, 2009](#); [Kilian, 2014](#); [Arezki et al., 2014](#); [Caldara et al., 2019](#)). The energy sector—including oil, natural gas, and electricity markets—is particularly sensitive to external shocks, often leading to volatility spillovers across different commodities ([Pindyck & Rotemberg, 1990](#); [Zhang & Wu, 2018](#); [Mohammadi & Parvaresh, 2014](#)).

Historically, oil and natural gas prices have exhibited strong co-movements, particularly during global crises such as the 1973 Oil Embargo, the 2008 Global Financial Crisis (GFC), and the 2022 Russia-Ukraine War ([Baffes, 2007](#); [Kilian, 2009](#); [Izzeldin et al., 2023](#)). The extent to which oil and gas price shocks impact electricity markets, however,

remains a subject of debate, with some studies suggesting a robust correlation between energy prices and electricity prices (Apergis & Payne, 2014; Zhang et al., 2021), while others argue that the transmission is more limited (Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018). This section will explore these varying perspectives and provide insight into the evolving relationship between oil, natural gas, and electricity prices, particularly in the context of recent geopolitical events.

To illustrate the relationship between Brent crude oil, natural gas, and UK electricity prices over time, a time series comparison is presented in *Figure 1: Trends in Commodity Prices (2021-2023)*. This chart highlights the fluctuations in commodity prices from 2021 to 2023, providing essential context for the analysis of price linkages discussed in this section.

2.2 OIL, NATURAL GAS, AND ELECTRICITY PRICE LINKAGES

The electricity market is complex, with prices being determined by a variety of factors, including generation costs, demand fluctuations, transmission constraints, and regulatory interventions (Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018; Sovacool, 2021). In liberalized electricity markets, such as that of the UK, electricity prices are often influenced by marginal cost pricing mechanisms, where the most expensive fuel source sets the market price for electricity. Since natural gas has become the most widely used fuel in the UK’s electricity generation sector, its price plays a crucial role in shaping electricity prices (Caldara et al., 2019; Zhang & Wu, 2018).

Figure 4: Histogram of UK Electricity Price Variability (2021-2023)

Although crude oil prices have historically been an important determinant of energy market fluctuations, their direct impact on electricity prices has diminished over time due to the declining role of oil-fired power generation. The shift towards natural gas has reduced the correlation between oil prices and electricity prices, making gas prices the dominant driver of electricity price volatility in modern energy markets. As highlighted by Caldara et al. (2019),

oil prices now mainly influence electricity markets indirectly, through their effects on inflation, transportation costs, and broader macroeconomic conditions.

In contrast, the relationship between natural gas and electricity prices is much more direct. [Zhang et al. \(2018\)](#) demonstrate that natural gas prices are closely tied to electricity prices, particularly in markets where gas-fired plants set the marginal cost of electricity generation. This link was evident during the UK energy crisis of 2022, where skyrocketing natural gas prices directly translated into record-high electricity prices. Several studies have further confirmed the dominance of natural gas in driving electricity price volatility ([Woo et al., 2006](#); [Brown and Yücel, 2008](#); [Mohammadi, 2009](#); [Chae, Kim, and Yoo, 2012](#); [Nakajima & Hamori, 2013](#); [Apergis & Payne, 2014](#); [Alexopoulos, 2017](#); [Uribe, Guillen & Mosquera-López, 2018](#); [Behnam Zakeri et al., 2023](#)). The 2022 energy crisis, characterized by surging natural gas prices due to supply disruptions, resulted in unprecedented electricity price hikes across Europe, including the UK ([IEA, 2022](#); [Behnam Zakeri et al., 2023](#)).

To visualize the correlation between natural gas prices and electricity prices, [Figure 2: Scatter Plot of Natural Gas Prices vs. UK Electricity Prices \(2021-2023\)](#) presents a scatter plot comparing the daily movements of these two variables from 2021 to 2023. The positive correlation observed in the scatter plot reinforces the importance of natural gas prices in determining electricity pricing trends in the UK.

Empirical studies on commodity price linkages suggest that while oil and gas markets frequently move together, the pass-through effect to electricity prices is not always immediate ([Baffes, 2007](#); [Zhang et al., 2021](#)). Some findings suggest natural gas prices exert a stronger influence, whereas crude oil's effect is often indirect, impacting transportation, industrial costs, and inflationary pressures ([Caldara et al., 2019](#); [Pindyck & Rotemberg, 1990](#)).

2.3 GEOPOLITICAL AND ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTY IN ENERGY MARKETS

Geopolitical events, particularly those involving major energy producers, play a significant role in shaping energy markets. The ongoing Russia-Ukraine war, which began in February 2022, stands out as one of the most significant geopolitical shocks affecting global energy prices in recent years. [Izzeldin et al. \(2023\)](#) document the immediate impact of the war on oil, gas, and electricity prices, showing that supply chain disruptions, economic sanctions, and market speculation have led to extreme volatility in energy markets.

Energy markets are particularly vulnerable to geopolitical risks and economic uncertainty ([Baker et al., 2021](#); [Caldara et al., 2019](#); [Behnam Zakeri et al., 2023](#)). The Russia-Ukraine conflict, in particular, has demonstrated how geopolitical shocks can amplify market volatility, leading to supply shortages, price hikes, and investor uncertainty. Several indices, such as the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), and the FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS), have been developed to quantify the level of uncertainty in

energy markets during times of crisis. [Zhang \(2018\)](#) further suggests that GPR is a key determinant of energy prices, as heightened uncertainty discourages investment in energy infrastructure, which can exacerbate price volatility. Empirical research supports this notion, with [Baker, Bloom & Davis \(2021\)](#) demonstrating that high levels of EPU amplify energy price fluctuations by discouraging long-term investments in energy production.

Research suggests that geopolitical crises often induce price volatility, but the extent of their influence on electricity prices remains debated ([Pindyck & Rotemberg, 1990](#); [Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018](#)). While the 2022 energy crisis was largely driven by gas shortages, macroeconomic conditions—interest rate hikes, inflation, and policy interventions—further complicated the pricing landscape ([IEA 2022](#); [Sovacool, 2021](#)).

Figure 5: Trends in Economic Indicators in the UK (2021-2023)

2.4 THE ROLE OF POLICY AND MARKET REGULATION

Market regulations play a critical role in electricity price stabilization during energy crises ([Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018](#); [Sovacool, 2021](#)). In response to the 2022 energy crisis, the UK government implemented an energy price cap to shield consumers from extreme fluctuations ([IEA, 2022](#)).

Historically, interventions such as subsidies for renewable energy, carbon pricing mechanisms, and capacity markets have aimed to enhance energy security ([Apergis & Payne, 2014](#)). Some studies argue that greater renewable energy adoption can reduce reliance on volatile fossil fuels, stabilizing long-term prices ([Sovacool, 2021](#); [Baffes, 2007](#); [Balcilar et al., 2019](#); [Zhang et al., 2023](#)). However, critics highlight the challenges of intermittency and integration costs ([Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018](#)).

Empirical evidence suggests that policy uncertainty itself can contribute to volatility—as seen during the UK’s shifting energy strategies post-Brexit ([Baker et al., 2021](#); [Zhang & Wu, 2018](#)).

The effectiveness of policy interventions depends on their implementation and market response. During the 2008 financial crisis, UK policymakers focused on demand-side incentives, carbon pricing, and investment in renewables to mitigate energy cost fluctuations ([The UK Renewable Energy Strategy, 2009](#)). In contrast, the 2022 energy crisis required more immediate consumer protection measures, such as energy price caps and windfall taxes on energy companies, to counteract the effects of rising wholesale gas prices ([HM Treasury, 2022](#)).

Table 3 provides a structured comparison of policy responses to these crises, highlighting key regulatory changes, financial support mechanisms, and their implications for energy market stability. This comparison underscores the evolution of UK energy policies and their role in mitigating external shocks while balancing long-term sustainability and affordability.

Policy Measure	2008 Crisis	2022 Crisis
Energy Price Cap	No	Yes
Windfall Tax on Energy Companies	No	Yes
Government Subsidies for Consumers	Yes	Yes
Increase in Renewable Energy Investments	Yes	Yes
Strategic Oil & Gas Reserves Release	Yes	Yes
Demand Reduction Measures	No	Yes
Expansion of Domestic Gas Production	Yes	No
Electricity Market Reform	No	Yes
Short-Term Financial Support for Businesses	No	Yes
Energy Efficiency Programs	Yes	Yes

Table 3: Comparison of Energy Policy Interventions in Past Crises (2008 vs. 2022)

2.5 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN PREVIOUS RESEARCH

A variety of econometric models have been used to analyze the impact of commodity price fluctuations on electricity pricing. Time-series models, such as those employed by [Hamilton, 2009](#) and [Pindyck & Rotemberg \(1990\)](#), are commonly used to examine co-movements between commodity prices. Other models, such as Vector Autoregression (VAR), have been used to capture shock transmissions across energy markets ([Moutinho et al., 2011](#); [Nakajima et al., 2013](#); [Caldara et al., 2019](#)). Granger causality tests are frequently applied to determine causal relationships between oil, gas, and electricity prices ([Mohammadi, 2009](#); [Moutinho et al., 2011](#)).

In this study, multiple regression analysis is employed to quantify the impact of Brent crude oil, natural gas, and macroeconomic uncertainty indices on UK electricity prices. **Figure 6** presents a flowchart outlining the model selection and analysis approach used in this research, detailing the steps from data preprocessing to regression modelling.

Figure 6: Flowchart of Model Selection and Analysis Approach

2.6 CONCLUSION AND RESEARCH GAP

Despite the wealth of research on commodity price volatility, there remain gaps in understanding the joint influence of Brent crude oil, natural gas, and macroeconomic indices on electricity prices (Hamilton, 2009; Zhang et al., 2021). Additionally, while some studies have explored the global impacts of the 2022 energy crisis, there is limited research on the UK market’s specific response to this crisis (Izzeldin et al., 2023). Furthermore, much of the existing research relies on quarterly or annual data, leaving gaps in understanding short-term volatility (Baffes, 2007; Kilian, 2014).

This study addresses these gaps by providing a UK-specific empirical analysis using high-frequency data and integrating multiple factors—energy prices, geopolitical risk, and macroeconomic indices—into a single econometric model. It also explores the post-2022 crisis dynamics by comparing pre- and post-crisis periods, offering valuable insights into how the energy crisis has altered electricity price linkages and policy interventions in the UK.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This study adopts a quantitative research design, utilizing time-series econometric modelling to examine the relationship between UK electricity prices and key influencing factors such as natural gas prices, Brent crude oil prices, geopolitical risk, economic policy uncertainty, and UK stock market trends. The research follows a deductive approach, with hypotheses and models grounded in existing theoretical frameworks on commodity price interdependencies, energy market volatility, and macroeconomic uncertainty ([Hamilton, 2009](#); [Zhang et al., 2018](#); [Baffes, 2007](#)). The central aim of this research is to quantify how these various factors impacted electricity prices before and after the 2022 energy crisis, with a particular focus on the influence of the geopolitical events surrounding the Russia-Ukraine war and the UK's energy price interventions.

In order to assess the relationships between electricity prices and their key drivers, this study integrates several analytical techniques. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis are used to provide an initial understanding of the relationships between the relevant variables. Multiple regression models are then employed to investigate three specific research questions:

The first research question examines the extent to which natural gas and Brent crude oil prices impact UK electricity prices. The second question investigates how post-2022 geopolitical events have altered the relationship between these commodity prices and electricity prices. The third question explores the role of broader economic indicators, such as the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), and the FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS), in explaining variations in electricity prices.

A time-series econometric approach is particularly suited to this study as it allows for the identification of long-term trends, cyclical patterns, and causality relationships among economic variables ([Pindyck & Rotemberg, 1990](#); [Caldara et al., 2019](#)). By analysing the temporal relationships between electricity prices and commodity prices, the study provides actionable insights into how energy price volatility and macroeconomic uncertainties influence electricity pricing in the UK.

To address these questions, the study adopts logarithmic returns rather than absolute prices in the regression models. This transformation normalizes variations across variables and accounts for volatility, which is essential for capturing the behaviour of financial time series. Furthermore, the research incorporates structural break analysis, which allows for the identification of shifts in price behaviour before and after major geopolitical events, such as the Russia-Ukraine war and the introduction of the UK's energy price cap. This approach will shed light on how such external shocks have altered the dynamics of electricity pricing.

3.2 DATA SOURCES AND SAMPLE SELECTION

The dataset for this study spans from January 2021 to December 2023, covering the pre-energy crisis, energy crisis, and post-energy crisis periods. The data sources used are all publicly available and reputable, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in the analysis. The primary datasets included in this research are the UK electricity prices dataset, natural gas prices dataset, Brent crude oil prices dataset, GPR index dataset, UK EPU dataset and FTSE All share Index dataset.

The UK System Price of Electricity dataset, sourced from the Office for National Statistics (ONS) 2023, is used as the dependent variable in the regression models. This dataset provides daily price data for electricity, measured in British Pounds per Megawatt-hour (£/MWh). The prices are transformed into logarithmic returns to analyze fluctuations over time, as electricity prices are directly impacted by fuel costs and broader macroeconomic conditions.

The System Average Price (SAP) of Natural Gas, sourced from National Gas Transmission and the ONS (2023), is used as an independent variable in the models. This dataset, measured in pence per kilowatt-hour (p/kWh), is converted to GBP per MWh for consistency with the electricity price data. Logarithmic returns are computed to account for price volatility, given the strong relationship between gas prices and electricity prices in the UK, as noted by [Apergis & Payne \(2014\)](#).

The Europe Brent Spot Price FOB, sourced from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), serves as another independent variable. This dataset, in dollars per barrel (USD/barrel), is converted to GBP using historical exchange rates. The price data is also transformed into logarithmic returns to capture the volatility inherent in oil prices, which indirectly influence electricity pricing through transportation, inflationary pressures, and market speculation ([Kilian, 2014](#); [Hamilton, 2009](#)).

The GPR dataset, sourced from the Policy Uncertainty Database ([Caldara & Iacoviello, 2019](#)), is included as a control variable in the model. This index, which tracks global geopolitical tensions, is available monthly and is transformed into logarithmic returns, interpolated for daily alignment. The GPR is included to account for the impact of geopolitical uncertainty on investment in energy infrastructure ([Zhang et al., 2018](#)).

The UK Daily EPU Index, sourced from the Policy Uncertainty Database ([Baker, Bloom & Davis, 2021](#)), captures the level of uncertainty regarding government policies in the UK. It is included as another control variable in the regression models. The index is transformed into daily logarithmic returns to reflect policy-driven fluctuations in market behaviour.

The FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS) dataset, sourced from Investing.com, provides daily data on the FTAS Index, a broad measure of UK market confidence. The index, expressed in GBP, is included as a control variable in the models to account for broader financial market trends that may influence energy consumption and electricity prices.

The sample period includes a total of 755 trading days, excluding weekends and public holidays, to ensure consistency across datasets. This period includes the pre-crisis period (January 2021 – December 2021), the crisis period (January 2022 – December 2022), and the post-crisis period (January 2023 – December 2023). By comparing these sub-periods, the study aims to determine whether the relationships between electricity prices, energy commodities, and macroeconomic variables strengthened or weakened over time.

3.3 REGRESSION FRAMEWORK AND MODEL SPECIFICATION

The research questions are addressed using multiple regression analysis, with each model tailored to examine the specific relationships outlined in the research questions. The regression framework includes both base and extended models to capture the impact of various economic and geopolitical factors on electricity prices. The base models focus on natural gas and Brent crude oil prices, while the extended models incorporate geopolitical risk and economic uncertainty indices.

3.3.1 RQ-1: Are natural gas and Brent crude oil prices significantly correlated with UK electricity prices?

The first regression model quantifies the relationship between natural gas and Brent crude oil prices and UK electricity prices. The following base regression model is specified:

$$\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t) + \beta_2 \Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t) + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- $\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t)$ = Log return of UK electricity prices
- $\Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t)$ = Log return of natural gas prices
- $\Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t)$ = Log return of Brent crude oil prices
- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1, β_2 = Coefficients measuring the sensitivity of electricity prices to changes in natural gas and Brent oil prices respectively
- ϵ_t = Error term

If β_1 and β_2 are found to be significant, it will indicate that natural gas and oil prices strongly drive electricity prices. If natural gas prices are highly correlated with electricity prices (as indicated in previous research, e.g., [Apergis & Payne, 2014](#)), we expect its impact (β_1) to be statistically significant and positive. Given that Brent crude oil is not a primary electricity generation source in the UK, its impact (β_2) may be weaker or insignificant.

3.3.2 RQ-2: How have post-COVID geopolitical events influenced this relationship?

This research investigates the influence of post-2022 geopolitical events on the relationship between electricity prices and their key drivers, including natural gas prices, Brent crude oil prices, and broader economic uncertainties. The period from January 2022 to December 2022 is considered the crisis period, as it encompasses several key geopolitical and economic events that had a profound impact on global energy markets. These events include the Russia-Ukraine war, the UK energy crisis, and interest rate hikes, all of which significantly altered the dynamics of energy pricing.

The Russia-Ukraine war, which began in February 2022, triggered extreme volatility in global energy markets. As one of the largest global exporters of natural gas and crude oil, Russia's invasion of Ukraine disrupted supply chains and led to severe fluctuations in commodity prices. These disruptions were particularly impactful on natural gas and oil markets, which are crucial inputs for electricity generation in the UK. The war, combined with subsequent sanctions imposed by Western nations on Russian energy exports, led to a substantial rise in energy prices across Europe, including the UK.

In addition to the geopolitical conflict, the UK energy crisis that unfolded throughout 2022 further exacerbated electricity price volatility. From April to October 2022, the UK experienced an unprecedented rise in wholesale gas and electricity prices. This crisis was largely driven by a combination of supply shortages, high demand during the post-pandemic recovery phase, and significant price increases for natural gas, which directly influenced electricity pricing.

Furthermore, interest rate hikes by the Bank of England played a critical role in shaping the economic landscape during 2022. The Bank of England raised interest rates five times throughout the year in response to rising inflation, which significantly impacted economic activity and energy demand. The rate hikes, ranging from 0.5% in February to 3.5% by December, contributed to increased financial costs for businesses and households, potentially affecting electricity consumption patterns and market behaviours.

For this study, the period of January 2022 to December 2022 is designated as the crisis period because it encapsulates these key events and their direct effects on energy prices. The focus on this period is justifiable because it represents a time of extreme volatility, marked by the combined effect of the Russia-Ukraine war, the UK energy crisis, and macroeconomic shifts due to monetary policy interventions. The pre-crisis period (January 2021 to December 2021) is characterized by the post-pandemic recovery phase, with rising energy demand but without the acute geopolitical and economic shocks of 2022. The post-crisis period (January 2023 to December 2023) represents the market's adjustment to new economic conditions, following the significant shocks of 2022.

To assess whether the relationship between electricity prices and their key drivers changed due to these geopolitical and economic events, this study introduces a dummy variable to differentiate between the pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods. This dummy variable,

Dummy_PostCrises, takes the value of 0 for the pre-crisis period (January 2021 to December 2021) and 1 for the crisis period (January 2022 to December 2022). The dummy variable allows the regression model to capture structural breaks and measure whether the influence of key factors on electricity prices significantly changed during the crisis. The revised regression model therefore is:

$$\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * [\Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t)] + \beta_2 * [\Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t)] + \beta_3 * [\Delta \ln(\text{GPR}_t)] + \beta_4 * [\Delta \ln(\text{EPU}_t)] + \beta_5 * [\Delta \ln(\text{FTAS}_t)] + \beta_6 * [\text{Dummy_PostCrises}] + \beta_7 * [(\Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t) * \text{Dummy_PostCrises})] + \beta_8 * [(\Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t) * \text{Dummy_PostCrises})] + \beta_9 * [(\Delta \ln(\text{GPR}_t) * \text{Dummy_PostCrises})] + \beta_{10} * [(\Delta \ln(\text{EPU}_t) * \text{Dummy_PostCrises})] + \beta_{11} * [(\Delta \ln(\text{FTAS}_t) * \text{Dummy_PostCrises})] + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- $\Delta \ln(\text{GPR}_t)$ = Log return of Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR)
- $\Delta \ln(\text{EPU}_t)$ = Log return of UK Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU)
- $\Delta \ln(\text{FTAS}_t)$ = Log return of FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS)
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and β_5 measure the pre-crisis impact of natural gas, Brent crude oil, geopolitical risk (GPR), economic policy uncertainty (EPU), and FTAS on electricity prices.
- β_6 captures the shift in electricity price behaviour due to geopolitical crises.
- $\beta_7, \beta_8, \beta_9, \beta_{10}$ and β_{11} measure whether the impact of natural gas, Brent oil, GPR, EPU and FTAS respectively changed during the crisis period.
- **Dummy_PostCrises** will be 1 for dates after 2022 crises (January 2023 – December 2023) and 0 for dates before 2022 crises (January 2021 – December 2021)

In addition, Table 4 below provides a detailed list of the interest rate hikes by the Bank of England in 2022, highlighting the timing and extent of monetary policy changes throughout the crisis period.

Date	Interest Rate (%)
03-Feb-22	0.50
17-Mar-22	0.75
05-May-22	1.00
16-Jun-22	1.25
04-Aug-22	1.75
22-Sep-22	2.25
03-Nov-22	3.00
15-Dec-22	3.50

Table 4: List of Bank of England Interest Rate Hikes in 2022

This table clearly illustrates the Bank of England’s gradual increase in interest rates over the course of 2022, highlighting the central bank’s response to rising inflation and

economic instability. The rate hikes had significant implications for the broader economic environment and energy markets, influencing electricity pricing dynamics.

By incorporating this period-specific analysis, this study aims to isolate the effects of the geopolitical crisis and the policy interventions on electricity prices, providing a clearer understanding of how these events have altered market behaviour and price relationships.

3.3.3 RQ-3: Do broader economic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) have a more pronounced impact on electricity prices compared to natural gas and Brent crude oil prices?

To explore the impact of broader economic uncertainties on electricity prices, this study employs three distinct regression models. The first model, referred to as the ‘**Energy-Only Model**’, focuses solely on the relationship between electricity prices and energy commodity prices, specifically natural gas and Brent crude oil. This model seeks to quantify how changes in energy commodity prices influence electricity prices, controlling for these variables alone. It is designed to isolate the effect of natural gas and oil price fluctuations on electricity prices, addressing the first part of the third research question.

$$\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t) + \beta_2 \Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t) + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- $\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t)$ = Log return of UK electricity prices
- $\Delta \ln(\text{NatGas}_t)$ = Log return of natural gas prices
- $\Delta \ln(\text{BrentOil}_t)$ = Log return of Brent crude oil prices
- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1, β_2 = Coefficients measuring the sensitivity of electricity prices to changes in natural gas and Brent oil prices respectively
- ϵ_t = Error term

The second model, the ‘**Economic-Uncertainty Model**’, shifts focus from energy prices to broader macroeconomic factors. In this model, electricity price returns are regressed on the log returns of the Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR), the Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU), and the FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS). This approach allows us to examine how uncertainty in geopolitical and economic conditions influences electricity prices, independent of energy prices. The objective here is to assess whether factors such as geopolitical tensions, policy uncertainty, and overall market sentiment have a stronger impact on electricity prices compared to energy commodities.

$$\Delta \ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * [\Delta \ln(\text{GPR}_t)] + \beta_2 * [\Delta \ln(\text{EPU}_t)] + \beta_3 * [\Delta \ln(\text{FTAS}_t)] + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- $\Delta\ln(\text{GPR}_t)$ = Log return of Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR)
- $\Delta\ln(\text{EPU}_t)$ = Log return of UK Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU)
- $\Delta\ln(\text{FTAS}_t)$ = Log return of FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS)
- β_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Coefficients measuring the sensitivity of electricity prices to changes in GPR, EPU and FTAS respectively
- ϵ_t = Error term

The third model, the ‘**Combined Model**’, integrates both energy prices and broader economic uncertainties, creating a more comprehensive framework. In this model, electricity price returns are regressed on the log returns of natural gas, Brent crude oil, GPR, EPU, and FTAS. This combined approach enables us to examine the relative importance of energy commodity prices versus macroeconomic variables in explaining electricity price fluctuations. By comparing the coefficients and adjusted R² values across all three models, this study aims to determine which set of factors—energy prices or macroeconomic uncertainties—provides a stronger explanatory power for electricity price movements.

$$\Delta\ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * [\Delta\ln(\text{NatGas}_t)] + \beta_2 * [\Delta\ln(\text{BrentOil}_t)] + \beta_3 * [\Delta\ln(\text{GPR}_t)] + \beta_4 * [\Delta\ln(\text{EPU}_t)] + \beta_5 * [\Delta\ln(\text{FTAS}_t)] + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- $\Delta\ln(\text{ElecPrice}_t)$ = Log return of UK electricity prices
- $\Delta\ln(\text{NatGas}_t)$ = Log return of natural gas prices
- $\Delta\ln(\text{BrentOil}_t)$ = Log return of Brent crude oil prices
- $\Delta\ln(\text{GPR}_t)$ = Log return of Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR)
- $\Delta\ln(\text{EPU}_t)$ = Log return of UK Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU)
- $\Delta\ln(\text{FTAS}_t)$ = Log return of FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS)
- β_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = Coefficients measuring the sensitivity of electricity prices to changes in Natural Gas, Brent Oil, GPR, EPU and FTAS respectively

This approach enables us to compare the explanatory power of energy prices vs. macroeconomic uncertainties by analysing Adjusted R² and p-values across different models. We will compute the regression results for the 3 models and compare their Adjusted R² values. The model with the highest R² will have the explanatory power for influencing electricity prices.

These models are designed to offer a detailed understanding of the dynamics influencing electricity prices, allowing for a comparison of the impact of energy market variables versus broader economic and geopolitical factors. The results will help determine whether broader economic uncertainties, such as political risk and policy uncertainty, play a more pronounced role in driving electricity price fluctuations than the traditional energy drivers of natural gas and oil prices.

3.3.4 SUMMARY OF MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

Research Question	Regression Model	Independent Variables	Additional Factors
RQ-1: Are natural gas and Brent crude oil prices significantly correlated with UK electricity prices?	Base Model	Natural Gas, Brent Oil	None
RQ-2: How have post-COVID geopolitical events influenced this relationship?	Crisis Model with Dummy Variable	Natural Gas, Brent Oil	Dummy_Post Crises (Pre vs. Post Crisis)
RQ-3: Do broader economic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) have a more pronounced impact on electricity prices?	A - Energy-only model B - Economic Uncertainty model C - Combined Model	Natural Gas, Brent Oil, GPR, EPU, FTAS	None

Table 5: Summary of multi-variable regression models employed

3.4 SAMPLE SPAN AND DATA TRANSFORMATIONS

For robust analysis, this study uses logarithmic returns rather than absolute prices. This transformation addresses several challenges commonly encountered in financial and energy time series, including heteroskedasticity and non-stationarity. Additionally, data preprocessing involved removing weekends and public holidays to ensure consistency across datasets.

To standardize the data, the following conversions were made: natural gas prices were converted from p/kWh to GBP/MWh, and Brent oil prices were converted from USD/barrel to GBP/barrel using historical exchange rates. The dataset spans 755 trading days, covering the periods before, during, and after the 2022 energy crisis, and includes sub-period analyses to assess changes over time.

3.5 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

All data sources are publicly available and non-sensitive, ensuring ethical compliance. The study does not involve human subjects, confidential information, or proprietary datasets, eliminating privacy concerns. Furthermore, appropriate citations and attributions are provided to maintain academic integrity.

4. RESULTS

This chapter presents the empirical findings derived from both the exploratory data analysis and the multiple regression models, structured around the three key research questions (RQs). The aim of this analysis is to quantify the relationships between UK electricity prices, commodity prices (natural gas and Brent crude oil), and broader macroeconomic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS), particularly within the context of the 2022 energy crisis.

4.1 EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

Before conducting the regression analysis, exploratory data analysis (EDA) was performed to understand the underlying patterns in the data. This analysis included descriptive statistics, correlation matrices, and scatter plot visualizations, which helped identify the key relationships among the variables.

4.1.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 6 provides the summary statistics for the key variables, including their mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and percentile values, spanning from January 2021 to December 2023. These statistics offer a comprehensive overview of the distribution, volatility, and central tendencies of the variables involved in the study, such as electricity prices, natural gas prices, Brent crude oil prices, and macroeconomic indicators like the GPR, UK EPU, and FTAS.

Variable	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Stdev	25%	50%	75%
Electricity	14.19	11.30	1.77	77.79	9.20	8.13	11.30	17.49
Natural Gas	4.86	3.82	0.43	18.33	3.06	2.69	3.82	6.42
Brent Spot	84.70	82.57	50.37	133.18	15.68	74.29	82.57	92.86
GPR Index	120.62	107.45	58.42	318.95	49.42	88.17	107.45	132.86
UK EPU Daily	243.38	203.54	16.66	1657.06	170.79	150.22	203.54	284.44
FTAS	4071.12	4083.51	3641.93	4377.36	141.18	4000.37	4083.51	4164.13

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics

The data reveals that electricity prices exhibit substantial variability, with a mean of £14.19/MWh and a median of £11.30/MWh, indicating a right-skewed distribution. The minimum price was recorded at £1.77/MWh, while the maximum reached £77.79/MWh,

reflecting large price fluctuations, especially during periods of crisis. The high standard deviation (9.20) confirms the volatility in electricity prices, which aligns with the dramatic price swings observed in 2022.

Natural gas prices demonstrate similar volatility trends, with a mean of £4.86/kWh and a significant maximum price of £18.33/kWh, compared to a minimum of £0.43/kWh. The standard deviation of 3.06 indicates considerable fluctuations, underscoring the role of natural gas prices as a key determinant of electricity prices. In contrast, Brent crude oil prices are relatively more stable, with a mean of £84.70 per barrel and a lower standard deviation (15.68). The maximum price of £133.18 per barrel and the minimum of £50.37 per barrel suggest moderate price fluctuations, but these remain less volatile than those of natural gas and electricity, supporting the finding that Brent oil does not directly impact electricity prices.

The Geopolitical Risk Index (GPR) displays wide variations, with a mean of 120.62 and a maximum of 318.95, which likely reflects spikes in geopolitical tensions, such as the Russia-Ukraine war. The standard deviation of 49.42 indicates substantial volatility in global geopolitical risk during the study period. Similarly, the UK Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) index shows significant variation, with a maximum value of 1657.06, pointing to the heightened uncertainty surrounding economic policies, particularly during key events like Brexit and the energy crisis. The FTSE All-Share Index, with a mean of 4071.12, exhibits relatively low volatility compared to energy prices, suggesting that equity market movements have a weaker influence on electricity prices.

Key insights from the descriptive statistics indicate that electricity and natural gas prices are highly volatile, driven by market shocks and supply disruptions. Brent crude oil prices, on the other hand, remain relatively stable, supporting the idea that oil has a weaker role in directly influencing electricity prices. The geopolitical risk index (GPR) and the economic policy uncertainty index (EPU) exhibit high volatility, suggesting that major global and domestic crises played a pivotal role in market disruptions, while the FTSE All-Share Index remained more stable.

4.1.2 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

To further explore the relationships among the variables, correlation matrices were computed, and the results are presented in Table 1: Daily Correlation Matrix and Table 2: Monthly Correlation Matrix. The correlation analysis reveals several key findings.

Electricity prices and natural gas prices exhibit a moderate positive correlation of 0.35, indicating that fluctuations in gas prices strongly influence electricity prices. In contrast, Brent crude oil prices show a near-zero correlation of -0.01 with electricity prices, suggesting a negligible direct impact. The correlation between macroeconomic indicators and electricity prices is weaker. The GPR shows a slight positive correlation of 0.15 with electricity prices, suggesting some sensitivity to geopolitical events, while the EPU and FTAS exhibit no

meaningful correlation (0.01 and -0.03, respectively), implying that broader economic conditions do not appear to be the primary drivers of electricity price movements.

These correlation findings support the inclusion of natural gas prices as a key independent variable in the regression models, while suggesting that Brent crude oil, GPR, EPU, and FTAS require further investigation in the regression analysis.

4.1.3 SCATTER PLOT ANALYSIS

To visualize the relationships, scatter plots were generated to show dependencies between electricity prices and key variables. The scatter plot of Electricity Prices vs. Natural Gas Prices reveals a strong clustering pattern, with notable outliers observed on June 13, 2022, and October 20, 2022. These outliers align with major events, such as interest rate hikes and price cap adjustments, which caused significant volatility in energy markets during these times. Please refer to [Figure 2: Scatter Plot of Natural Gas Prices vs. UK Electricity Prices \(2021-2023\)](#).

In contrast, the scatter plot of Electricity Prices vs. Brent Crude Oil Prices shows no visible trend, reinforcing the weak correlation observed earlier. The scatter plots for Electricity Prices vs. GPR, EPU, and FTAS also show no significant patterns, indicating that these macroeconomic indicators have a limited direct impact on electricity prices, although they may influence market dynamics in more complex ways. Please refer to [Figure 3: Scatter Plot of Brent Crude Oil Prices vs. UK Electricity Prices \(2021-2023\)](#).

Figures 7, 8 and 9 present the scatter plots for GPR, UK EPU, and FTAS against UK electricity prices, further supporting the weak relationships observed in the correlation analysis.

These findings provide valuable insights into the relationships among the key variables and set the stage for the regression analysis, where we further investigate the impact of these factors on electricity prices.

Figure 7: Scatter Plot of GPR vs. UK Electricity Prices (2021-2023)

Figure 8: Scatter Plot of UK EPU vs. UK Electricity Prices (2021-2023)

Figure 9: Scatter Plot of FTAS vs. UK Electricity Prices (2021-2023)

4.2 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The regression analysis is conducted to test the research hypotheses outlined in the study. Each regression model is tailored to answer a specific research question, with the primary focus on understanding the relationships between electricity prices and their key drivers, such as commodity prices, geopolitical risk, and economic uncertainties.

4.2.1 RQ-1: Are Natural Gas and Brent Crude Oil Prices Significantly Correlated with UK Electricity Prices?

A baseline regression model was used to examine the relationship between electricity price log returns as the dependent variable and natural gas log returns and Brent crude oil log returns as independent variables. The regression results indicate that a 1% increase in natural gas prices leads to an approximate 0.82% increase in electricity prices, suggesting a strong positive relationship between the two. In contrast, a 1% increase in Brent crude oil prices leads to a 0.27% decrease in electricity prices, but this relationship is statistically insignificant, confirming that Brent crude oil does not meaningfully drive electricity prices. The high adjusted R² (0.83) further supports the strong explanatory power of natural gas prices in explaining electricity price fluctuations.

Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value
Intercept	-0.0096	
Natural Gas Log Return	0.8212	1.56774E-13
Brent Oil Log Return	-0.2729	0.3326

Table 7: Regression output for RQ-1

So, the conclusion for RQ-1 is - Natural gas is significantly correlated with UK electricity prices, but Brent crude oil is not.

4.2.2 RQ-2: How Have Post-COVID Geopolitical Events Influenced This Relationship?

To test the impact of the 2022 energy crisis, a crisis dummy variable and interaction terms were introduced in the regression model. The results show that geopolitical risk (GPR) has become a more significant driver of electricity prices post-crisis, with a positive coefficient (0.88) and a p-value of 0.067. This suggests that heightened geopolitical tensions post-crisis have contributed to greater volatility in electricity prices. Additionally, Brent crude oil prices have gained explanatory power, with a positive coefficient (2.56) post-crisis, indicating that electricity prices are now more sensitive to oil price fluctuations, possibly due to increased reliance on oil following gas market disruptions. Natural gas, however, lost statistical significance post-crisis, with a p-value of 0.961, suggesting that its role in driving electricity prices has diminished.

Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value
Intercept	0.0483	
Natural Gas Log Return (Pre-Crises)	0.7346	0.0192
Brent Oil Log Return (Pre-Crises)	-2.7380	0.0341
GPR Log Return (Pre-Crises)	-0.7860	0.0576

UK EPU Log Return (Pre-Crises)	-0.0090	0.9527
FTSE All-Share Log Return (Pre-Crises)	5.2095	0.2157
Dummy (Post Crises)	-0.0741	0.4667
Natural Gas Log Return (Post Crises)	-0.0176	0.9608
Brent Oil Log Return (Post Crises)	2.5634	0.0644
GPR Log Return (Post Crises)	0.8796	0.0674
UK EPU Log Return (Post Crises)	-0.0296	0.9097
FTSE All-Share Log Return (Post Crises)	-6.5113	0.1895

Table 8: Regression output for RQ-2

So, the conclusion for RQ-2 is - The post-2022 crisis period has heightened the impact of geopolitical risk (GPR) and Brent oil prices on electricity prices while reducing the significance of natural gas. UK EPU remains an insignificant predictor, while the FTAS Index shows a minor shift in its relationship with electricity prices. These findings suggest that policymakers should focus on energy diversification and geopolitical risk management to mitigate electricity price volatility in times of crisis.

4.2.3 RQ-3: Do Broader Economic Uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) Have a More Pronounced Impact on Electricity Prices Compared to Natural Gas and Brent Crude Oil?

Three regression models were used to answer this question, with the combined model showing the highest adjusted R² value, indicating that the combination of energy prices and economic uncertainty indices explains electricity prices better than either factor alone. The energy-only model, with an adjusted R² of 0.83, confirms that natural gas prices and Brent crude oil are the primary drivers of electricity prices, while the economic uncertainty model has a much lower adjusted R² of 0.037. This suggests that broader economic uncertainties have a less pronounced impact on electricity prices compared to commodity prices.

Tables 9, 10 and 11 are regression outputs for RQ-3:

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value	Model fit (R ² Value)
Intercept	-0.0098		0.8267
Natural Gas Log Return	0.8212	1.56774E-13	
Brent Oil Log Return	-0.2729	0.3327	

Table 9: Regression output for RQ-3 (a) - Energy only model

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value	Model fit (R ² Value)
Intercept	-0.0114		0.0374
GPR log return	0.2676	0.3181	
UK EPU log return	-0.1033	0.6376	
FTAS log return	0.4408	0.8799	

Table 10: Regression output for RQ-3 (b) - Economic Uncertainty Model

Variable	Coefficient (β)	p-value	Model fit (R^2 Value)
Intercept	-0.0068		0.8331
Natural Gas Log Return	0.8360	2.39844E-12	
Brent Oil Log Return	-0.3204	0.2926	
GPR log return	-0.0399	0.7389	
UK EPU log return	0.0799	0.4063	
FTAS log return	-0.1712	0.8929	

Table 11: Regression output for RQ-3 (c) - Combined Model

So, the conclusion for RQ-3 is - Broader economic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) do impact electricity prices, but their effect is less pronounced compared to commodity prices, especially natural gas. However, when combined with energy prices, they improve the model's explanatory power, suggesting that economic uncertainties and energy markets jointly influence electricity prices.

4.3 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The findings from the regression analysis are summarized in **Table 12**, highlighting the key insights from each research question. For RQ-1, natural gas prices significantly influence UK electricity prices, while Brent crude oil prices are statistically insignificant. In RQ-2, the post-2022 crisis period saw an increased impact of geopolitical risk and Brent oil prices on electricity prices, while natural gas prices lost significance. Finally, RQ-3 reveals that economic uncertainties impact electricity prices, but their effect is secondary to that of commodity prices, especially natural gas.

Research Question	Key Findings
RQ-1	Natural gas prices significantly impact UK electricity prices. Brent crude oil is insignificant.
RQ-2	Post-2022, geopolitical risk and Brent oil gained significance in electricity pricing, while natural gas impact declined, emphasizing the need for energy diversification and risk management.
RQ-3	Economic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) influence electricity prices but are secondary to natural gas, though they enhance the model when combined with energy prices.

Table 12: Summary of Results

These findings provide strong empirical evidence that energy market factors, rather than macroeconomic uncertainties, are the primary drivers of UK electricity price fluctuations.

5. DISCUSSION

This chapter interprets the empirical findings presented in Chapter 4, linking them to existing literature and theoretical frameworks, and discussing their broader policy implications. By connecting the results to prior studies and market dynamics, we identify key consistencies, deviations, and new insights that contribute to the ongoing discussions in energy economics and policy formulation. The chapter also assesses how the 2022 energy crisis reshaped the relationship between electricity prices, commodity markets, and macroeconomic factors. The discussion is structured around the research questions, examining how the findings align with or diverge from past studies and what they imply for future energy policy and market stability.

5.1 NATURAL GAS, BRENT CRUDE OIL AND UK ELECTRICITY PRICES (RQ-1)

Our results confirm that natural gas prices have a strong and statistically significant correlation with UK electricity prices, a finding consistent with previous literature ([Apergis & Payne, 2014](#); [Mohammadi & Parvaresh, 2014](#)). This outcome aligns with the structure of the UK's energy market, where natural gas plays a dominant role in electricity generation. However, Brent crude oil prices were found to be an insignificant predictor of electricity prices, contrasting with studies that emphasize the link between oil and electricity prices in more oil-dependent economies ([Hamilton, 2009](#); [Kilian, 2014](#)).

One explanation is that while oil prices influence broader energy markets, their direct effect on electricity pricing in the UK is minimal due to limited oil-based power generation. Instead, the UK's electricity system is primarily driven by gas-fired plants and renewables. This is supported by prior research suggesting that oil price shocks have an indirect impact on electricity costs through transportation, production costs, and investor sentiment rather than direct fuel input costs ([Baffes, 2007](#); [Zhang & Wu, 2018](#)).

These results highlight the need for policymakers to ensure a stable natural gas supply while considering long-term strategies to reduce dependency on fossil fuels. Investments in renewable energy technologies and battery storage could help mitigate the impact of natural gas price fluctuations and strengthen energy security ([Sovacool, 2021](#); [Borenstein & Bushnell, 2018](#)).

The findings are consistent with previous studies such as those by [Apergis & Payne \(2014\)](#), who found that natural gas prices have a more direct influence on electricity markets compared to oil. Furthermore, [Baffes \(2007\)](#) demonstrated that commodity price linkages exist but vary in intensity, with our study showing that oil has a weaker influence on electricity pricing. However, our results deviate from [Borenstein & Bushnell \(2018\)](#), who argued that electricity pricing is increasingly decoupling from fossil fuels due to renewable energy adoption. In contrast, our study suggests that gas remains a dominant force in the UK electricity market.

The key takeaway from this section is that, while global shifts towards renewables are evident, the UK's electricity market remains highly exposed to natural gas volatility. This highlights the urgent need for faster energy diversification to reduce dependence on fossil fuels.

5.2 IMPACT OF POST-2022 GEOPOLITICAL CRISES ON ELECTRICITY PRICES (RQ-2)

The regression analysis for RQ-2 revealed a notable shift in the relationship between electricity prices and its key determinants after 2022. Specifically, the significance of natural gas prices weakened post-crisis, while geopolitical risk (GPR) and Brent crude oil prices gained greater explanatory power. This finding aligns with [Izzeldin et al. \(2023\)](#), who reported increased market volatility and structural shifts in commodity price behaviour following geopolitical disruptions such as the Russia-Ukraine war.

The heightened impact of Brent oil prices in the post-crisis period suggests greater spillover effects from global energy markets into electricity pricing. This could be due to increased economic uncertainty, shifts in investor sentiment, and indirect costs such as supply chain disruptions and inflationary pressures ([Caldara et al., 2019](#); [Zhang et al., 2021](#)). The weakening effect of natural gas prices post-2022 could be attributed to regulatory interventions, including government-imposed energy price caps ([HM Treasury, 2022](#)). Additionally, market adjustments, such as increased LNG imports and diversification of energy sources, may have reduced the direct pass-through effect of gas price volatility to electricity costs ([IEA, 2022](#)).

These results underscore the importance of geopolitical risk management and energy diversification. The UK government's energy strategy should focus on insulating the electricity market from external shocks by accelerating investments in renewable energy, improving energy storage capacity, and strengthening trade agreements for alternative gas supplies ([Baker et al., 2021](#); [Zhang & Wu, 2018](#)).

5.3 THE ROLE OF BROADER ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTIES (RQ-3)

RQ-3 examined whether macroeconomic indicators (GPR, EPU, FTAS) had a stronger impact on electricity prices than commodity prices. Our findings suggest that while economic policy uncertainty (EPU) remained statistically insignificant, geopolitical risk (GPR) and FTSE All-Share Index (FTAS) played a moderate role in explaining electricity price variations. These results contrast with previous studies that found stronger linkages between economic policy uncertainty and energy prices, such as [Baker et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Balcilar et al. \(2019\)](#). However, our findings are consistent with [Sovacool \(2021\)](#), who noted that geopolitical factors often have a more immediate and direct effect on energy prices compared to policy uncertainty.

The relationship between FTAS and electricity prices also warrants discussion. A minor shift in FTAS's influence post-2022 suggests that investor confidence and stock market dynamics may play a secondary role in electricity pricing. This aligns with [Pindyck & Rotemberg \(1990\)](#), who noted that financial markets can drive speculative price movements in energy commodities but are less impactful in fundamentally driven markets like electricity. Overall, these findings emphasize that commodity prices remain the primary drivers of UK electricity prices but incorporating geopolitical and economic factors improves the model's explanatory power.

In conclusion, the results from RQ-3 suggest that while broader economic uncertainties do have some impact on electricity prices, their effect is secondary to that of commodity prices, especially natural gas. Nonetheless, when combined with energy prices, these economic factors contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of electricity price dynamics. Policymakers should, therefore, consider integrating market-based energy strategies with broader macroeconomic and geopolitical risk assessments.

5.4 POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, several key policy recommendations emerge. First, given the strong relationship between natural gas prices and electricity costs, policies should focus on stabilizing gas supply chains through diversified imports, storage expansions, and increased investments in LNG infrastructure. Second, the findings underscore the importance of enhancing energy security in the face of geopolitical risks. The increased significance of geopolitical risk post-2022 highlights the need for the UK to establish diplomatic energy partnerships and alternative supply routes to mitigate the effects of external shocks.

Furthermore, the results suggest that the UK government should accelerate the transition to renewable energy. By scaling up renewable energy generation and investing in grid storage solutions, the UK can reduce its reliance on natural gas and improve long-term energy stability. Finally, while macroeconomic factors were secondary in their impact, investor sentiment and economic uncertainty can indirectly influence electricity pricing. Policymakers should ensure that financial regulations complement energy market stability strategies to avoid exacerbating price volatility.

5.5 CONTRIBUTIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study contributes to the existing literature by providing a UK-specific empirical analysis of electricity price determinants, integrating commodity prices, macroeconomic indicators, and geopolitical risks. While this research offers valuable insights, several limitations should be noted. The study's timeframe, spanning from 2021 to 2023, limits the analysis of long-term trends. Additionally, data aggregation issues, such as the mismatch

between daily electricity prices and monthly GPR data, may affect the precision of some results. The lack of granular energy mix data also poses a limitation, as the study assumes gas remains the dominant source of electricity generation, while actual power generation proportions fluctuate over time.

Future research could address these limitations by expanding the dataset to include real-time renewable energy contributions, assessing their role in price volatility. Another avenue for future work is to investigate sector-specific electricity price pass-through effects, such as those in industrial versus residential consumers. Moreover, applying advanced econometric techniques, such as machine learning models or structural vector autoregression (SVAR), could provide a deeper understanding of nonlinear relationships in energy price dynamics and improve price prediction accuracy.

6. CONCLUSION

This study has explored the relationship between UK electricity prices, commodity prices, and broader macroeconomic uncertainties, particularly in the context of the 2022 energy crisis. Our empirical findings contribute to the ongoing discussions in energy economics and policy formulation by highlighting several key insights.

First, we confirm that natural gas remains the dominant driver of electricity pricing in the UK, consistent with the structure of the nation's energy market. However, the impact of natural gas prices has diminished since the onset of the 2022 energy crisis. This shift suggests that while gas remains crucial to electricity generation, its influence is now more susceptible to external shocks, including geopolitical events and oil price fluctuations.

Second, the results show that geopolitical risk and Brent crude oil prices have gained greater explanatory power in the post-2022 period. The heightened volatility in global energy markets, particularly due to the Russia-Ukraine war and subsequent supply disruptions, has led to an increased role for these factors in shaping electricity prices. This marks a significant departure from previous years, where natural gas prices predominantly influenced market dynamics.

Additionally, macroeconomic uncertainties, while still relevant, have played a secondary role in explaining electricity price movements. The findings suggest that while policy uncertainty and broader economic factors such as the FTSE All-Share Index are factors in market behaviour, their impact on electricity pricing is less pronounced compared to commodity prices and geopolitical risks.

The 2022 energy crisis has therefore marked a structural shift in the UK's electricity market. Geopolitical risks and oil prices are now more influential, highlighting the importance of energy diversification and robust risk management strategies. The diminishing role of natural gas, coupled with the heightened influence of external factors, calls for a more proactive approach to energy policy. Policymakers must focus on increasing the resilience of the electricity market by investing in renewable energy sources, enhancing energy storage capacities, and securing alternative energy supplies to mitigate the impact of future geopolitical and economic shocks. By addressing these insights, policymakers can develop more effective strategies to safeguard the UK's electricity market from potential crises in the future.

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8. APPENDICES

Appendix A: Research Proposal

Introduction

This appendix contains the original research proposal submitted prior to conducting the study, which outlined the research objectives, methodology, and expected contributions. The proposal served as the foundation for this dissertation, helping define the scope, structure, and approach to analyzing the impact of the 2022 energy crisis on UK electricity prices.

The key elements of the research proposal are summarized below for quick reference:

The title of the study is *"Analysing the Impact of the 2022 Energy Crisis on UK Electricity System Prices."* The study sought to answer the following research questions:

- RQ1: Are natural gas and Brent crude oil prices significantly correlated with UK electricity prices?
- RQ2: How have post-COVID geopolitical events influenced this relationship?
- RQ3: Do broader economic uncertainties (GPR, EPU, FTAS) have a stronger impact than energy prices?

The methodology employed regression analysis with electricity prices as the dependent variable, including control variables such as the Geopolitical Risk (GPR) Index, Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) Index, and FTSE All Share (FTAS) Index. The study also included exploratory data analysis (EDA) using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and time-series visualizations.

The expected contributions of the research were to provide UK-focused insights into energy market volatility, assess the role of economic uncertainty in electricity pricing, and inform policy strategies for energy price stabilization.

The complete research proposal is included as a linked document for full transparency and to facilitate replication of the study: [PriyankaNaik_ResearchProposal_Final Version.pdf](#)

Appendix B: Ethics Approval and Considerations

This appendix outlines the ethical considerations adhered to during the research process, ensuring compliance with academic integrity, data protection regulations, and responsible research practices. The study followed Liverpool John Moores University's (LJMU) ethical guidelines and conformed to established ethical frameworks for conducting business and financial research.

The research was based entirely on secondary data sourced from publicly available datasets. As no human participants were involved, and no confidential or proprietary data were used, the study did not require ethical approval for primary data collection. The research did, however, comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principles, ensuring that all datasets were sourced from official, publicly accessible repositories, thus safeguarding data privacy and transparency.

The study took several ethical considerations into account throughout its course. First, data transparency and integrity were prioritized by ensuring that all datasets used in the research were from reputable, publicly available sources, including the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS) for electricity and gas prices, the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) for Brent crude oil prices, and the Policy Uncertainty Database for the Geopolitical Risk (GPR) and Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) indices. No manipulation, misrepresentation, or selective reporting of data was undertaken.

In terms of academic integrity and plagiarism prevention, proper citation and referencing of all sources were followed, using the Harvard referencing style. To ensure the originality of the research, Turnitin or similar plagiarism detection tools were employed to verify that the work was free from any unethical practices.

The study was designed to avoid bias, and multiple regression analysis alongside exploratory data analysis (EDA) were employed to ensure objectivity in the results. The methodology was structured to prevent any selective reporting or cherry-picking of results, as all relevant independent and control variables were included in the analysis.

Furthermore, the results of the study were interpreted responsibly, ensuring that no exaggeration or overgeneralization of findings occurred. Any limitations of the study, including potential biases in the data sources or methods, were transparently acknowledged in Chapter 5, Section 5.5, titled *Contributions and Future Research Directions*, which discusses the potential impacts of these limitations on the overall conclusions of the research.

To provide full transparency and facilitate replication of the study, the complete ethics form for secondary research is included as a linked document here: [Ethics Form Secondary Research Form B_Priyanka Naik_VP.pdf](#)

Appendix C: Data Sources and Preprocessing Steps

This appendix provides an overview of the data sources used in the study and the preprocessing steps undertaken to ensure the consistency, accuracy, and suitability of the data for analysis. The study relies on publicly available datasets sourced from reputable and authoritative sources, ensuring that all data used is transparent and reliable.

The first dataset used is the UK Electricity Prices dataset, which was sourced from the UK Office for National Statistics (ONS). This dataset provides daily system prices for electricity in the UK, measured in pounds per megawatt-hour (£/MWh). The second dataset is the Natural Gas Prices dataset, also sourced from the UK ONS. It includes daily system average gas prices in pence per kilowatt-hour (p/kWh), reflecting fluctuations in the natural gas market, which is a key factor in electricity pricing in the UK.

Additionally, the study incorporated the Brent Crude Oil Prices dataset, which was sourced from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA). This dataset provides daily spot prices for Brent crude oil, measured in dollars per barrel (USD/barrel), and serves as an important benchmark for global energy markets. The Geopolitical Risk (GPR) Index dataset, sourced from the Policy Uncertainty Database, provides monthly data on geopolitical risks that impact global markets, including energy. The UK Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) Index, also sourced from the Policy Uncertainty Database, provides daily uncertainty metrics related to UK economic policies. Lastly, the FTSE All-Share Index dataset, sourced from Investing.com, represents overall UK stock market performance and was included as a control variable in the analysis.

To ensure the datasets were suitable for regression analysis, several preprocessing steps were undertaken. Missing data, particularly for weekends and public holidays when markets are closed, was handled with careful consideration. For electricity, natural gas, and Brent oil prices, missing values (weekends and holidays) were deleted. For the GPR Index, which is reported monthly, the same value was applied across all days within the corresponding month to maintain consistency. Similarly, for the FTSE All-Share Index, missing values for weekends and holidays were linearly interpolated based on the values from the previous and subsequent trading days.

Unit standardization was also an important step in data preprocessing. Electricity prices were already in £/MWh, so no conversion was needed. The natural gas prices, originally reported in pence per kilowatt-hour, were converted to £/MWh for direct comparison with electricity prices. Brent crude oil prices, reported in dollars per barrel, were converted to pounds per barrel using daily exchange rates obtained from Investing.com. The FTSE All-Share Index, already measured in GBP, did not require any conversion.

To address volatility and ensure the data was stationary, log returns were calculated for all variables using the formula: $\text{Log Return} = \ln(\text{Price at time } t / \text{Price at time } t-1)$. This transformation normalizes the data, helping to stabilize the variance and making the variables more suitable for regression analysis. Additionally, weekends and public holidays were

removed from the dataset, as financial markets and energy trading do not occur during these times. This step ensured that there were no artificial distortions in the data trends.

A binary dummy variable was created for RQ-2 to distinguish between the pre-crisis and post-crisis periods. The pre-crisis period was defined as January 2021 to December 2021, and the post-crisis period as January 2022 to December 2022. This allowed the study to assess the impact of the 2022 energy crisis on the relationship between electricity prices and other variables. Data for the post-stabilization period (January 2023 to December 2023) were excluded from the analysis for RQ-2 to focus on the immediate aftermath of the crisis.

Lastly, two correlation matrices were constructed to examine the relationships among key variables. The first matrix used daily data to assess correlations between electricity prices, natural gas prices, oil prices, the EPU index, and the FTSE All-Share Index. The second matrix used monthly data to examine broader trends, particularly the relationship between electricity prices and the GPR Index. These correlation matrices provided important preliminary insights into the relationships between the variables before moving on to more advanced regression analysis.

These preprocessing steps were designed to ensure that the datasets were clean, consistent, and aligned, providing a strong foundation for the subsequent regression analysis. The use of log returns, unit conversions, missing data handling, and the creation of dummy variables helped refine the model's accuracy and interpretability, enabling a robust analysis of the impact of energy market dynamics and economic uncertainty on UK electricity prices.

Appendix D: Exploratory Data Analysis and Regression Outputs

This appendix presents the key outputs from the Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) and Multiple Regression Analysis conducted to assess the characteristics, relationships, and patterns in the dataset.

To provide full transparency and facilitate replication of the research, the complete excel analysis is included as a linked document here: [Thesis Analysis_28022025.xlsx](#)

Appendix E: Additional Literature Review References

This appendix provides an extended list of academic papers, policy reports, and institutional publications that were consulted during the research process but were not directly cited in the main chapters. These references offer broader context on the energy crisis, market volatility, and policy interventions. The summaries highlight how each source informed the development of the research framework and enhanced the understanding of energy market behavior and regulatory responses.

One important reference is the [*World Bank \(2023\). "Commodity Markets Outlook – Energy Prices"*](#) which provided a comprehensive overview of oil and gas market volatility during 2022–23 and its transmission to developing economies. This report was instrumental in shaping the initial framing of the research problem, particularly regarding the global impacts of energy price fluctuations.

The study by [*Asche, F., Osmundsen, P. and Sandsmark, M. \(2006\). "The UK Market for Natural Gas, Oil and Electricity: Are the Prices Decoupled?"*](#) examines the long-term price relationships among the UK's natural gas, oil, and electricity markets using cointegration techniques. The authors found that while these energy markets were historically integrated, there is growing evidence of decoupling, especially between electricity and oil, owing to market liberalization and shifts in generation sources. This research is highly relevant to the current study as it supports the investigation into the differentiated impacts of oil and natural gas prices on electricity pricing in the UK, particularly during crises such as the one in 2022.

Another relevant study is [*van Ruijven, B. and van Vuuren, D.P. \(2009\). "Oil and natural gas prices and greenhouse gas emission mitigation"*](#) which explores how fluctuations in oil and natural gas prices influence the cost and feasibility of greenhouse gas mitigation strategies. The authors used energy system modeling to demonstrate that high fossil fuel prices accelerate the shift toward low-carbon technologies and enhance the cost-effectiveness of renewable energy adoption. This finding provides important context to the study's policy implications, particularly the idea that high gas prices during the 2022 energy crisis could catalyze the UK's transition toward renewable energy.

The meta-analysis by [*Labandeira, X., Manzano, B., & Rodríguez, M. \(2017\). "A Meta-Analysis on the Price Elasticity of Energy Demand"*](#) provided insights into demand-side responses to energy price changes. This study was valuable for interpreting the policy implications discussed in Chapter 5 of this dissertation.

In [*Djørup, S., Thellufsen, J.Z. and Sorknæs, P. \(2018\). "The electricity market in a renewable energy system"*](#) the authors examine the transformation of electricity markets in systems with high renewable energy penetration, focusing on market design, pricing mechanisms, and flexibility requirements. The study highlights the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating variable renewable sources such as wind and solar, particularly in terms of grid stability and price volatility. This research is relevant for

understanding UK policy responses and market adaptations during the 2022 energy crisis, especially regarding the role of renewables in mitigating price shocks.

Dechezleprêtre, A. et al. (2020). "Energy price shocks and firm productivity: Evidence from EU industry" investigates how energy price shocks influence firm-level output, which helped shape the discussion in Chapter 5 regarding the long-term economic implications of energy price volatility.

Deane, J.P., Ó Ciaráin, M. and Ó Gallachóir, B.P. (2017). "An integrated gas and electricity model of the EU energy system to examine supply interruptions" presents a detailed energy systems model that integrates both gas and electricity markets across the EU. The study explores the impacts of fuel supply interruptions, revealing how gas supply shocks can cascade into electricity systems, causing significant price volatility and system instability. This work supports the rationale for analyzing gas-electricity price linkages, which is crucial in understanding the 2022 energy crisis.

In Gross, R., Hanna, R., Gambhir, A., & Heptonstall, P. (2018). "How long does innovation and deployment of energy technologies take?" the authors explore the timeline for the innovation and deployment of energy technologies. This study provided valuable context in understanding the role of renewables and the UK's energy transition policies.

Pezzutto, S., Grilli, G., Zambotti, S. and Dunjic, S. (2018). "Forecasting Electricity Market Price for End Users in EU28 until 2020—Main Factors of Influence" investigates electricity price forecasts for end users across the EU28. The authors identify key influencing factors such as fuel prices, carbon pricing, and policy instruments. This study provides a baseline for evaluating the deviations in electricity pricing during the 2022 energy crisis and supports comparative analysis within this dissertation.

The UK Renewable Energy Strategy. (2009) outlines the UK government's long-term commitment to increasing the share of renewable energy in electricity, heating, and transport. It sets legally binding targets and provides the foundation for regulatory reforms and financial incentives to support clean energy adoption. This strategy document is particularly relevant when contextualizing how past energy policies aimed at reducing fossil fuel dependence can be compared with more recent interventions during the 2022 energy crisis.

Stern, D. (2011). "The Role of Energy in Economic Growth" offers a foundational discussion on energy as a core input in macroeconomic models. This study provided background for Chapter 1, which discusses electricity market dynamics.

The work by Lorde, T., Jackman, M., & Thomas, C. (2009). "The macroeconomic effects of oil price fluctuations on a small open economy" is relevant for understanding the transmission mechanisms of oil shocks to domestic prices, helping to frame the macroeconomic context of energy price volatility in this study.

Díaz, G., Coto, J. and Gómez-Aleixandre, J. (2019). "Prediction and explanation of the formation of the Spanish day-ahead electricity price through machine learning regression" uses machine learning models to predict electricity prices in Spain. Although focused on Spain, the study provides methodological relevance to the UK electricity market, particularly in enhancing forecasting accuracy during volatile periods like the 2022 energy crisis.

The European Commission (2022). "REPowerEU Plan" outlines the EU's strategic policy response to accelerate renewable energy adoption and reduce dependence on Russian gas. This document provided useful context for comparing national-level responses to the energy crisis, particularly the UK's policy shift during the same period.

OECD (2020). "The effect of energy prices and environmental policy stringency on manufacturing employment in OECD countries: Sector- and firm-level evidence. OECD Economics Department Working Papers" investigates how energy price fluctuations and environmental regulations affect employment in manufacturing sectors. The findings offer important context for understanding how energy crises can ripple through economic sectors, reinforcing the thesis's broader discussion on the importance of stabilizing energy prices for economic resilience.

The Europa.eu. (2022) report discusses the EU's REPowerEU Plan, which outlines strategies to reduce reliance on Russian fossil fuels. This document provides context for evaluating national-level responses like the UK's and aligns with the thesis's focus on long-term policy shifts in response to energy crises.

Chen, X. (2022). "Are the shocks of EPU, VIX, and GPR indexes on the oil-stock nexus alike? A time-frequency analysis. Applied Economic" explores the varying effects of economic policy uncertainty (EPU), the Volatility Index (VIX), and the Geopolitical Risk (GPR) index on oil prices and the stock market. This study reinforced the inclusion of the GPR and EPU indices in this research as control variables affecting electricity prices through their influence on oil and broader financial markets.

Finally, Pata, U.K., Alola, A.A., Erdogan, S. and Kartal, M.T. (2023). "The influence of income, economic policy uncertainty, geopolitical risk, and urbanization on renewable energy investments in G7 countries." investigates how economic and geopolitical indicators affect renewable energy investments across G7 nations. This paper supports the inclusion of the GPR and EPU indices in the regression models analyzing UK electricity prices.

These references, while not directly cited in the main chapters, significantly contributed to shaping the design of research questions, the construction of regression models, and the development of the policy context discussed in Chapters 2 and 5.

Appendix F: Personal Research Reflection

This appendix provides a personal reflection on the research process, detailing the challenges faced during data collection and analysis, key takeaways from conducting the research, and lessons learned on energy market dynamics and policy decision-making.

One of the primary challenges faced was consolidating reliable, high-frequency datasets for the various energy prices and economic indicators. Ensuring consistency across datasets with varying frequencies, units, and formats required substantial effort in data cleaning and preprocessing. Additionally, selecting appropriate econometric models and interpreting complex regression outputs added to the analytical complexity of the study.

Conducting this research significantly enhanced my ability to handle large, multidimensional datasets and apply quantitative techniques like time series analysis and regression. It also sharpened my critical thinking in making methodological trade-offs, such as using log returns for stationarity or excluding certain variables based on statistical significance.

The research reinforced the importance of proactive and well-communicated government policies in stabilizing energy markets during crises. Insights from the study are highly relevant for policymakers and financial decision-makers seeking to enhance resilience in the energy sector.